

STRUCTURE OF ABILITIES AT DIFFERENT AGE PERIODS

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Abstract

In this article, information on the structure of abilities in different age periods is studied, and the qualitative description of abilities also reveals which individual psychological characteristics of a person serve as a mandatory condition for the success of the activity.

Key words: ability, age periods, personality, pedagogy, psychology, social life.

In psychology, abilities are described as individual psychological characteristics, and based on this, the characteristics and qualities of one person differ from another person. Therefore, it is impossible to expect the same result and the same quality from the same person, because people differ from each other to a certain extent in terms of their abilities, therefore, there can be a lot of differences between them in terms of quality and quantity. . The qualitative description of abilities means which individual psychological characteristics of a person serve as a necessary condition for the success of an activity. The description of their quantity indicates the ability of a person to fulfill the requirements for the activity, that is, it shows how quickly, easily, and thoroughly this person can use skills and knowledge compared to other people.

In order to create a general understanding of abilities, it is appropriate to provide some information on the factors and contents related to them:

- a) abilities are psychological characteristics of a person;
- b) the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and qualifications depends on these characteristics;
- c) these characteristics themselves do not apply to knowledge, skills and qualifications.

Based on the analysis of the above facts, a firm decision could be made on the abilities of individuals based on the evaluation of goods, successful or unsuccessful participation in contests. According to psychological studies, an "average" student in the process of higher education, according to the mastery index, later changes in a positive direction, achieves high results in another branch (network), and finds himself in a specialty close to his specialty. can show. In the experience, there are many cases where people who are uneducated and considered "unsuitable" in education and social life later become leading experts in any field, occupy high positions, and mature as entrepreneurs. Therefore, although abilities are manifested in the

process of acquiring (mastering) knowledge, skills, and qualifications, they are not directly related to knowledge, skills, and qualifications, for the same reason, they interact with each other and when analyzed from a relative point of view, abilities and knowledge, abilities and skills differ from each other in terms of content, content, and meaning. When this psychological happiness is explained in a more figurative way, if knowledge is imagined as a concrete reality acquired through training, skills are the unrealized potential of a person in the Russian world. For example, a student's enrollment is embodied as an opportunity for professional development as a specialist (his aspirations, objective and subjective health, health, etc.), individual abilities are manifested as an opportunity to acquire professional knowledge, skills and qualifications. Whether professional knowledge and skills were acquired or not, whether the opportunity came true or remained as an unfulfilled dream - all this depends on many factors and circumstances.

For example, people in the environment (family, school, team members, community) are interested in a person's acquisition of skills in this or that field of knowledge, attitude to study, teaching, and responsibility for their organization and strengthening. All such as doing is the realization of the possibility, the guarantee of its transformation into reality.

According to the methodological basis of psychology, it is made up of a system of abilities and opportunities, and the necessary level of expertise in this or that activity is considered reality. A person's visual art ability cannot guarantee his formation as an artist. Special education, special attitude to nature, ability to perceive, personal quality, health, fabrics, brushes, paints, appropriate tools, etc. Without the above-mentioned tools and conditions, visual art skills can disappear at the very beginning, before they develop. Of course, it is not a secret to anyone that in the course of social and historical development, there have been countless such incidents.

While denying that abilities and knowledge, skills and competences, which are important aspects of activity, are the same thing, the science of psychology recognizes their unity. Therefore, abilities are realized only in activity, but then the commandment of the candle to be realized without these abilities is reflected only in the forms of activity. If a person has not learned how to paint, then there is no reason to think about his abilities in relation to visual arts, because he cannot master the skills of visual art. All this depends on how quickly and easily the artist learns the work style, methods, color relationships, perceives and imagines the beauty of the candle.

The calculated activity that a person must occupy, regardless of whether it is a pleasant education, pleasant work, pleasant game, pleasant sport, imposes certain requirements on his cognitive processes, mental qualities, emotional-volitional aspects, sensorimotor area, characterological characteristics. yadi and success will be achieved due to their efforts in candle making. According to psychological data, even if the quality achieved in a person has a high priority, he will not be able to meet the requirements. The mental characteristic (characteristic) manifested in some cases of paralysis has the ability to ensure the high efficiency and effectiveness of the activity, and the hypothesis that the strength is equal to the ability to achieve it does not justify itself. Therefore, it is very appropriate to say that abilities are a set of mental qualities (characteristics) with a complex structure.

Due to the fact that the structure of the complex of mental qualities, which are realized as abilities, is clearly and distinctly defined by the activity requirement, it is a matter of what kind of activities the sphere is placed in a unique way. For this, we will analyze some examples:

1) Mathematical ability: Summarizing abstract materials, shortening the process of thinking, reducing abstract actions, establishing a connection between the perception of a problem and its result, easy transition from direct and indirect thinking, dexterity of thinking in problem solving. such as;

2) literary ability; The high level of development of the glasses of sophistication, vivid visual images in the memory, "til zeshni", boundless imagination, interest in Russian, desire for self-expression, etc. As it can be seen from the composition of the distinguished abilities, the mathematical and literary abilities differ from each other with their dissimilar requirements. From this it can be concluded that the structure of pedagogical, musical technical, constructive, medical skills and similar skills has a special character and can gain professional importance. Among the characteristics and qualities of a person, which make up the structure of obvious abilities, some of them play an auxiliary role.

Conclusion: It is known that pedagogical decency (tact), love of children, organization and management of a group of students, observability, demandingness, thirst for knowledge, ability to transfer knowledge and the like are recognized as leading qualities in the structure of pedagogical skills.

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